

IDEA 2013

Indian Distance Education Association (IDEA) organised the IDEA-2013 International Conference at the Maulana Azad National Open University (MANUU) on April 5 - 7, 2013. About 200 delegates, including representatives from Sri Lanka, Pakistan, and Bangladesh participated in the conference. The Conference took off to a stimulating start on 5th of April 2013 with the inauguration of the event by Shri Jitin Prasada, Hon'ble Minister for State for HRD, Govt of India. He highlighted the role of open and distance learning in

the 21st Century. Shri Prasada laid stress on the need for the education sector to meet the increasing demands from all stakeholders and also emphasised the need to educate for employment and empowerment, providing access and equity to serve as a support mechanism for the disadvantaged groups.

The main objectives of the conference were to share ideas, information and experiences on different issues, methods and technologies for quality assurance, standardization and delivery of education beyond borders. Under the theme "Disseminating Learning, Diminishing Borders - ODL in 21st Century" the

conference discussed quality concerns and best practices in open and distance learning, social networking and collaborative learning, learners' support and learning communities, user friendly technologies, research and development, capacity building, language barriers, women in ODL etc. Prof. V. S. Prasad, presented Prof. G Ram Reddy Memorial Lecture, on "The Disconnect between Dharma and Karma in Indian ODL".

(Report by Dr. Mushtaq Ahmed I. Patel)

Book Review

Open Educational Resources: An Asian Perspective

GAJARAJ DHANARAJAN and DAVID PORTER (Eds), *Commonwealth of Learning, Vancouver, 2013, pp. xvii, 274, ISBN 978-1-894975-61-2 (pbk)*

By Dr. S. K. Pulist

The Commonwealth of Learning (COL) is leading the Open Educational Resources (OER) movement across the globe. While its main thrust is on 'learning for development', it uses OER to increase access to quality learning resources. The book under review, jointly published by COL and OER Asia, with support from Wawasan Open University (WOU), Malaysia and International Development Research Centre (IDRC), Canada provides a comprehensive overview of country reports from China, Hong Kong, India, Indonesia, Japan, Korea, Malaysia, Pakistan, Philippines and Vietnam and ten

different case studies undertaken on OER movements in higher education institutions in the Asian region.

The development of OER activities in Asian region is presented in this volume from different perspectives. The book is divided into three main parts - 'Overview', 'Country Perspectives' and 'Case Studies', further sub-divided into 20 Chapters in all. Each Chapter shares an exclusive experience with the readers. The 'Overview' by Dhanarajan and Abeywardena presents the current scenario on OER in the Asian region. The authors see the OER movement as a 'way of addressing the dual challenge of

quality and equity'. However, they are concerned about the knowledge, effective use and policy provisions with regard to OER. While *Chapter 1* presents the current status of OER initiatives and development in the mainland China, *Chapter 2* presents result of a survey conducted in Hong Kong on the development and use of OER. In *Chapter*